

1 **Downscaling of MODIS Leaf Area Index Using Landsat Vegetation Index**

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11 **Downscaling of MODIS Leaf Area Index Using Landsat Vegetation Index**

12 Several organizations provide satellite Leaf Area Index (LAI) data regularly, at various
13 scales, at high frequency, but at low spatial resolution. This study attempted to enhance the
14 spatial resolution of the MODIS LAI product to the Landsat resolution level. Four
15 climatically diverse sites in Europe and Africa were selected as study areas. Regression
16 analysis was applied between MODIS Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) and LAI data. The
17 regression equations were used as input in a downscaling model, along with Landsat EVI
18 images and land-cover maps. The estimated LAI values showed high correlation with field-
19 measured LAI during the dry period. The model validation gave statistically significant
20 results, with correlation coefficient values ranging from relatively low (0.25–0.32), to
21 moderate (0.48–0.64) and high (0.72–0.94). Limited samples per vegetation type, the
22 diversity of species within the same vegetation type, land-use/land-cover changes and
23 saturated EVI values affected the accuracy of the downscaling model.

24 **Keywords:** LAI, EVI, downscaling model, regression analysis, high resolution

25 **Introduction**

26 The Leaf Area Index (LAI) is an important parameter characterizing vegetation and is widely
27 used to describe activities within an ecosystem, such as the monitoring of plant growth stages
28 (J. Clevers, 1989). LAI data are also used in hydrological models operating at river basin or
29 sub-basin level (Schumann, 1993) and especially in the estimation of water related
30 parameters (Pedro et al., 2011), in order to define the water loss by evapotranspiration, as

31 well as the roughness for surface water flow. Ideally, input LAI data should be acquired at as
32 high spatial resolution and frequency (depending on the examined vegetation type) as
33 possible, in order to describe accurately the development of vegetation.

34 LAI data can be acquired either through fieldwork, or remotely, using satellite or
35 airborne sensors. Measurement of LAI in the field is a laborious and costly process and can
36 be achieved with direct (ground-based), or indirect methods, such as taking vertical
37 photographs of the canopy with a hemispherical lens and processing the acquired photos with
38 specialized software (T. K. Alexandridis, Stavridou, Strati, Monachou, & Silleos, 2013).
39 Satellite-based LAI is provided on weekly to monthly basis by a number of organizations,
40 such as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, [http://api.data.fao.org/1.0/query-api-](http://api.data.fao.org/1.0/query-api-builder.html)
41 [builder.html](http://api.data.fao.org/1.0/query-api-builder.html)), the European Space Agency (ESA,
42 <https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/lai>) and the National Aeronautics and Space
43 Administration (NASA, <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). Although the above-mentioned
44 satellite LAI products are characterized by high temporal resolution (8-10 days), their low
45 spatial resolution (300–1000 m) makes them useable mainly in regional and global studies,
46 while they are not suitable for local studies. At higher resolution, the recently developed
47 Biophysical Processor tool available through the Sentinel-2 toolbox of the SNAP software
48 (<http://step.esa.int/main/toolboxes/snap/>), offers the ability to automatically create Sentinel-2
49 imagery-based LAI data at a spatial resolution of 20 m. However, it is not possible to create
50 historical LAI datasets prior the launch period of the Sentinel-2 satellite in the orbit (2015),
51 thus, prior the date Sentinel-2 entered into operational acquisition mode. Therefore, for the
52 acquisition of historical LAI data (prior 2015) of high resolution, alternative methods and
53 data sources should be investigated.

54 The LAI, as well as the Vegetation Indices (VIs), are some of the most valuable tools
55 with a global use to monitor and evaluate the progress during plants' growth. Various studies

56 have demonstrated the use of VI's for the estimation of LAI. The most common index used in
57 relevant literature for the estimation of LAI is the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
58 (NDVI) (Wang, Adiku, Tenhunen, & Granier, 2005). Major disadvantage is that the NDVI is
59 not sensitive at medium to large LAI values. The Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) on the
60 other hand, is considered to be a more stable and accurate VI compared to the NDVI, while in
61 general these two indices have similar performance no matter what crops are analysed
62 (Colombo, Bellingeri, Fasolini, & Marino, 2003). Moreover, the EVI has improved
63 sensitivity in high biomass regions and according to Wang, Tenhunen, et al. (2005) the values
64 of EVI are more useful than those of the NDVI in estimating LAI. Even though NDVI is
65 considered to be more appropriate for estimating chlorophyll responsiveness of the
66 vegetation, the EVI is more sensitive to the variations of canopy structure (canopy
67 architecture, crown type, vegetation physiognomy and LAI) (Chen & Sun, 2010). An
68 additional advantage is that EVI normalizes and adjusts the reflectance in the red band as a
69 function of the reflectance in the blue band, minimizing this way the residual atmospheric
70 influence (Huete, Liu, Batchily, & Van Leeuwen, 1997).

71 Several studies have attempted to estimate LAI at high resolution using as input
72 satellite imagery. These studies are generally narrowed to only certain types of crops (J. G.
73 Clevers, Kooistra, & van den Brande, 2017; Walthall et al., 2004), certain types of forest
74 vegetation (Eklundh, Harrie, & Kuusk, 2001), or are limited to narrow-sized study sites. The
75 presented methods are usually dependent on in-situ observations for the training of the
76 algorithms and limited to a few sampled locations. In relevant literature Onojeghuo et al.
77 (2018) developed a methodology for MODIS LAI downscaling after analysing a 2-year
78 timeseries of LAI and NDVI data. However, this method can only find application in rice
79 paddies and may be influenced by the low sensitivity of NDVI at medium to large LAI
80 values. Houborg and McCabe (2018) exploited a Cubesat Enabled Spatio-Temporal

81 Enhancement Method (CESTEM) to optimize the utility and quality of very high-resolution
82 CubeSat imagery, resulting to the daily retrieval of NDVI and LAI at 3 m resolution via the
83 fusion of CubeSat, Landsat, and MODIS data. Although this methodology provides LAI data
84 of very high resolution (3 m), the acquisition of the input data used (CubeSat) is considered
85 as costly. Houborg, McCabe, Cescatti, et al. (2015) managed to retrieve LAI directly from at-
86 sensor radiances of Landsat data, using a fully integrated system of radiative transfer models
87 (applicable over most regions without the need for site-specific calibration) and information
88 extracted entirely from image-based and readily available datasets. Houborg, McCabe, and
89 Gao (2015) proposed a LAI downscaling methodology integrating a rule-based regression
90 tree approach for estimating Landsat-scale LAI using the MODIS LAI product at 1 km spatial
91 resolution and the Spatial and Temporal Adaptive Reflectance Fusion Model (STARFM), to
92 intelligently interpolate the downscaled LAI between Landsat acquisitions. In their method,
93 they also use MODIS NDVI data in order to first generate a finer resolution LAI map (250 m
94 instead the initial LAI map of 1km spatial resolution), which could assist to improve
95 predictability in heterogeneous agricultural landscapes and improve the accuracy of the
96 downscaling model. Similarly, Yu et al. (2018) obtained high resolution LAI by using a
97 regression tree approach and the spatial and temporal adaptive reflectance fusion model
98 (STARFM). Sun et al. (2017) developed a regression tree method for retrieving Landsat LAI
99 for grape yield prediction, using homogeneous and high quality MODIS LAI data as
100 reference. Ma, Duan, Li, and Song (2019) implemented a revised version of STARFM to
101 produce high-resolution LAI data for use in SWAT hydrological models. Zhang and He
102 (2016) developed a downscaling LAI method by training an Artificial Neural Network
103 (ANN) with MODIS LAI and NDVI data and Landsat-8 based estimated NDVI. Zhenhua,
104 Rugen, Yueming, Shudi, and Peihua (2016) developed a method for generating high
105 spatiotemporal resolution LAI based on MODIS/GF-1 data and combined Kriging-Cressman

106 interpolation. There are also approaches to study and estimate LAI at catchment area level,
107 using satellite data of various spatial resolutions (MODIS LAI 1km and MODIS NDVI 250
108 m, (Silleos et al., 2014).

109 This study attempted to develop a methodology for downscaling the coarse spatial
110 resolution of MODIS LAI images to higher resolution, using VI data of MODIS and Landsat
111 satellites. The focus was on developing a simple and easily applied downscaling
112 methodology, taking into account all vegetation types present in a river catchment, the
113 diversity of climatic conditions found in study sites around the globe, as well as the use of
114 satellite imagery that can be accessible free-of-cost.

115 **Materials and Methods**

116 *Study areas*

117 Four catchment areas in Europe and Africa ([Figure 1](#)) characterized by climatic diversity
118 were selected as study sites, covering a wide selection of natural vegetation types and
119 agricultural systems. This choice was made in order to investigate the performance of the
120 proposed methodology under various climatic conditions, since intra-species variability of
121 vegetation is highly climate-dependent. The main characteristics of each study area are
122 summarized in [Table 1](#). [Figure 1 and Table 1 near here].

123 *Data collection and pre-processing*

124 *MODIS LAI-EVI*

125 MODIS data (products MCD15A2-LAI and MOD13A2-EVI at 1 km spatial resolution) were
126 downloaded for each study area for the years 2012 and 2013 (according to in-situ LAI data
127 availability, see Table 4), from the United States Geological Survey platform (USGS,
128 <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>).

129 All pixels of good quality, according to the MODIS Quality Assurance (QA) data,
130 from the 8-day (MCD15A2) and the 16-day (MOD13A2) image composites were used in
131 subsequent analyses, excluding those falling on - or close to - the borders of different
132 vegetation types (mixed pixels). A total of 20 MODIS images (10 for the EVI product and 10
133 for the LAI product) have been used for the analysis, as presented in [Table 2](#). [Table 2 near
134 here]

135 *Landsat EVI*

136 Several atmospherically corrected and geo-referenced (UTM/WGS84) Landsat 7 and 8 EVI
137 images were downloaded for each study area and for dates coinciding with the field surveys
138 ([Table 3](#)), through the Land Satellites Data System (LSDS) Science Research and
139 Development (LSRD) platform provided by USGS (<https://espa.cr.usgs.gov/>). [Table 3 near
140 here]. The Landsat 7 EVI images included lines of no data, due to the sensor's scan-line
141 corrector malfunction. Gap-filling was not attempted to avoid inserting errors (T. K.
142 Alexandridis, Cherif, et al., 2013) during the comparison of the proposed methodology results
143 with the field measurements.

144 *Land Use / Land cover data*

145 A high resolution and a moderate resolution Land Use / Land Cover (LULC) map was
146 acquired for each study area, through EU FP7 project "MyWater" (see acknowledgments) for
147 the study purposes.

148 The Landsat derived LULC maps followed the Land Cover Classification System
149 (LCCS) developed by FAO. The initial classification of 12 LCCS classes was changed for the
150 study purposes, reducing the vegetation classes to 6 types of biomes, similar to those used by
151 the MODIS land-cover product (which is used as input in the MODIS LAI algorithm):
152 irrigated crops, rainfed crops, broadleaved forests, needleleaved forests, shrubs and grassland,

153 as presented in [Figure 2](#). The vegetation type maps were produced using spectral
154 classification techniques (Nunes, Araújo, Alexandridis, & Chambel, 2013), such as the
155 Maximum Likelihood Classifier (MLC), the majority voting fuser classifier and the multi-
156 stage classifier, on Landsat multispectral images and field surveyed data. Two Landsat
157 images acquired in different seasons were used per study site in order to account for different
158 phenological stages of vegetation and improve classification accuracy. The overall accuracy
159 of the high-resolution vegetation type maps was 89.43% (estimated kappa 0.8808) for Nestos,
160 88.16% (kappa 0.8331) for Rijnland, 86% (kappa 0.792) for Tamega and 85% (kappa 0.849)
161 for Umbeluzi. [Figure 2 near here]

162 The moderate resolution (300 m) GlobCover land-cover product for year 2009 was
163 also acquired for each study area, in order to be used together with the MODIS datasets. The
164 choice of the GlobCover dataset instead of the relevant MODIS LULC product, was made in
165 order to avoid the use of interdependent data in the proposed methodology, since the MODIS
166 LAI algorithm uses as input the MODIS LULC product. Additionally, the GlobCover dataset
167 uses a spatial resolution approximately three times finer than the MODIS pixel (300 m
168 instead of 1 km), so it was also feasible to determine the effect of mixed vegetation pixels and
169 further exclude any sample points representing such a state during the analysis of data (see
170 section Data collection and pre-processing – MODIS LAI-EVI). The Globcover data were
171 reclassified according to the 6 biome types also used in the Landsat LULC maps presented
172 above (irrigated crops, rainfed crops, broadleaved forests, needleleaved forests, shrubs and
173 grassland).

174 *In-situ LAI*

175 Field measured LAI data of 2012-2013 were acquired for all study areas through EU FP7
176 project “MyWater” (see acknowledgments), recorded at a seasonal time-step ([Table 4](#)).

177 Representative sites in each study area (22-37 locations, see Annex I for details) were
178 selected, covering all types of vegetation present (according to the 6 vegetation classes
179 presented in section Data collection – Land Use /Land Cover). For the selection of a suitable
180 sample design strategy, four key characteristics were used: the number of sample sites
181 required within each study area, the spatial distribution of the sample sites, the required size
182 of each sample site selected, as well as the number of subplots required (Brogaard &
183 Ólafsdóttir, 1997). [Table 4 near here]

184 A stratified random sampling approach was preferred rather than a random sampling
185 approach, in order to maintain a high level of accuracy and additionally reduce the number of
186 samples. The number of locations selected as samples is highly dependent on the size of the
187 study area, as well as on its spatial variability. Following the guidelines of Townshend and
188 Justice (1988) for the estimation of the required size of each sample site, the pixel size and
189 the geometric accuracy of the satellite images used were taken into consideration. Three
190 subplots were measured at each location, forming the corners (vertices) of a triangle with
191 dimensions equal to $2/3$ of the satellite image's pixel size and then the three results were
192 averaged. In cases of sparse vegetation or plantation, where great variability was expected, an
193 approach of taking measurements on the corners and the centre of each sample site was
194 followed. As a result of the sampling design, error inherent to sampling ranges from 7.5 (for
195 Nestos) to 12.5% (for Umbeluzi). The error could not be further reduced as this would lead to
196 a higher number of sample sites to be visited during field survey thus increasing the cost of
197 field work in terms of time, money, and effort.

198 A protocol for measuring LAI using hemispheric camera photographs was used in
199 order to ensure that the quality of the measurements would be as high as possible (T. K.
200 Alexandridis, Stavridou, et al., 2013). The technique used was to estimate the canopy
201 thickness by measuring the light transmission through the canopy. Hemispherical (use of

202 fish-eye lens) photographs in upward and downward direction were processed with
203 specialized software to estimate the field LAI values. In order to ensure that LAI estimates
204 would be comparable in time and space, it was considered essential to compensate for the
205 variable sun irradiance throughout the day and year, as well as under variable tree canopies.
206 Therefore, the exposure of the photographic camera used was calibrated relatively to the sky,
207 and this exposure was increased by two stops during image acquisition under the canopy
208 (Welles & Norman, 1991). Underexposure in near horizontal directions was avoided by using
209 a zenith angle range between 0 to 75° (van Wijk & Williams, 2005). In cases of low stature
210 vegetation, where distortions might be present to the LAI estimated values (van Wijk &
211 Williams, 2005), the hemispherical photographs were taken from above in a downwards
212 direction (Bréda, 2003).

213 The hemispherical photographs, were processed with CAN-EYE (freely available for
214 downloading at <https://www4.paca.inra.fr/can-eye/>) software for the downward direction and
215 with HEMISPHER software
216 (http://www.wsl.ch/dienstleistungen/produkte/software/hemisfer/index_EN) for the upward
217 direction, following a different approach for each of the two cases. The upward direction
218 photographs were processed based on gap-fraction identification, separating the canopy
219 (dark) from the sky (light) pixels. The photos of downward direction were processed by using
220 reflectance ratios, in order to identify the features on the photographs based on the spectral
221 behaviour of the examined wavelengths. The analysis of the downward direction photographs
222 was performed by grouping them according to the date each photograph was taken and to the
223 light conditions present. An automatic class pre-selection was applied, with the user
224 identifying or correcting after this step the final sample of vegetation and non-vegetation
225 pixels on a hemispherical photograph. As a next step, this sample was used for all the
226 photographs of each group, with an image classification process following, in order to

227 acquire photographs indicating two or three possible states: vegetative state, non-vegetative
228 state and mixed state. When this step was finished, CAN-EYE software automatically
229 calculated LAI values in multiple photographs, with the final results provided in a
230 spreadsheet. During the analysis of the upward direction photographs, the pixels were first
231 classified as sky (white) or canopy (black) by the application of a brightness threshold to each
232 picture analysed. The optimal threshold was estimated using the LAI-2000 method, as it is
233 reported to be closer to a standard reference (Stenberg, 1996). After this step, the light
234 transmission (T) was calculated as a proportion of the white pixels present in the
235 hemispherical photograph. Then the average number of times that a light ray would touch the
236 canopy when travelling a distance equal to the thickness of the canopy was estimated,
237 providing this way the contact number (K), which is described by the equation: $K = -\cos \Theta \ln$
238 T. Finally, the K values were integrated over the rings in order to estimate the LAI values.

239 ***Data processing***

240 *MODIS – Landsat EVI data comparison*

241 The MODIS and Landsat EVI products are computed according to the following equation:

$$\text{EVI} = G * ((\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / (\text{NIR} + C1 * \text{Red} - C2 * \text{Blue} + L)), \quad (1)$$

242 where G is the Gain factor (= 2.5), near infra-red (NIR), red and blue are atmospherically
243 corrected values of surface reflectance, L (= 1) is the factor for the canopy background
244 adjustment and C1 (= 6) - C2 (= 7.5) are the coefficients of the aerosol resistance term used
245 for the blue band, in order to correct aerosol influences in the red band. [Table 5 near here]

246 Since there are minor differences in the bandwidth values between the Landsat and
247 MODIS bands participating in the formulation of the EVI equation (see [Table 5](#)), the EVI
248 products of the two satellites intended to be used in the same downscaling model were
249 compared, to examine their compatibility. Therefore, for two of the study areas (Umbeluzi

250 and Tamega) and for dates with minimum possible cloud presence, Landsat and MODIS EVI
251 images of the same period were compared. The rescaling methodology involved grid
252 polygons (fishnets, see [Figure 3](#)) which were created per study area, matching the geometric
253 properties of the MODIS 1000 m spatial resolution LAI and EVI images (i.e., the square
254 polygons of the grid matched the footprint of the pixels of the MODIS 1000 m image).
255 During the comparison applied between the Landsat and MODIS EVI data, the mean value
256 per available MODIS 1000 m pixel (square polygon of the fishnet) was estimated, using all
257 the Landsat pixel values corresponding to the area covered by each MODIS pixel. For the
258 comparison, the images were cropped to the extent of the relevant study areas. [Figure 3 near
259 here]

260 *MODIS LAI-EVI data quality assurance*

261 Only the pixels indicated from the MODIS Quality Assurance (QA) data as of “good” quality
262 were taken into consideration during the analysis. Additionally, extreme values for LAI (<0 ,
263 >20) and for EVI (<0.1) were excluded, as they clearly did not represent any possible
264 vegetation state.

265 *Landsat data quality assurance and LULC classification*

266 For each Landsat image, its corresponding cloud mask (C implementation of Function of
267 Mask, CFMask) layer was used to exclude pixels of low quality and those not representing
268 vegetation (e.g., covered by snow/ice). Extreme EVI values (<0.1) were excluded in this case
269 too, as they clearly did not represent any possible vegetation state.

270 Using the Landsat LULC maps (presented in section Data collection - Land Use / Land
271 Cover), each pixel of the above-mentioned processed Landsat EVI images was classified
272 according to one of the six vegetation types described in section Data collection – Land Use /
273 Land Cover.

274 *MODIS LAI-EVI regression equations for the downscaling model*

275 The MODIS LAI-EVI relationship was examined through regression analysis, taking into
276 account both the characteristics of seasonality (Day of Year, DOY) and the vegetation type
277 (T. K. Alexandridis, Ovakoglou, & Clevers, 2019). The regression analysis was applied using
278 a linear fit ($y = a + b * x$) for each available pair of a MODIS LAI and EVI image of the same
279 period and for each study area, while the data were grouped per vegetation type.

280 *Downscaling model*

281 The estimated MODIS LAI-EVI regression equations per study area and vegetation type,
282 along with the processed Landsat EVI images, were used as input data in the downscaling
283 model ([Figure 4](#)), in order to estimate the LAI values at the Landsat spatial resolution. In this
284 model, the equations calculated per study area, vegetation class and date during the MODIS
285 LAI-EVI regression analysis, were used as formulas to estimate the LAI values for each
286 Landsat pixel, using the corresponding Landsat EVI values (classified per vegetation type) as
287 input in the regression equations. [Figure 4 near here]

288 *Downscaling model accuracy assessment*

289 The created LAI maps of all study areas and for all available time-periods were validated
290 using the available in-situ measured LAI data (presented in section Data collection – In-situ
291 LAI).

292 **Results**

293 *MODIS-Landsat EVI data compatibility*

294 The comparison between EVI values derived from MODIS data and the equivalent values
295 derived from Landsat data showed high R^2 (0.89 for Tamega and 0.87 for Umbeluzi, $p <$
296 0.001, see [Figure 5](#)). The mean difference was 0.031 (m^2/m^2). In both cases examined, the
297 differences between the MODIS and Landsat EVI products were minor and thus, the data

298 were evaluated as directly comparable and compatible for use in the downscaling model.
299 [Figure 5 near here].

300 *MODIS LAI-EVI regression analysis*

301 During the quality assurance check of the MODIS datasets, only pixels flagged as of “good
302 quality” were retained. After the application of the regression analysis, the equations that
303 connected MODIS LAI with MODIS EVI per date and vegetation type were generated for
304 each test site. An example of the regression analysis results for the study area of Umbeluzi on
305 DOY 193-2013 can be found in [Table 6](#), while a detailed presentation of all results is
306 available at T. K. Alexandridis et al. (2019). In all vegetation types of Umbeluzi, the
307 probability value (p) was <0.0001 . The R^2 ranged between 0.39 (lowest value for the
308 broadleaved forests due to the mixed tree and grass/shrubs vegetation) and 0.79 for the
309 grassland vegetation type. The moderate to high R^2 values found were estimated using a large
310 number of samples (N) and the offset and slope factors had similar values in all cases
311 examined. [Table 6 near here]

312 In the related scatter plots ([Figure 6](#)), most of the vegetation types of Umbeluzi show
313 low LAI and EVI values due to the dry climatic conditions present. Considering the rainfed
314 crops, which represent the main agricultural activity of the study area, the moderate R^2 found
315 is due to the existence of two different species of rainfed crops dominating the study area
316 (maize and pulses). Shrubs and grasslands show the lowest pairs of LAI and EVI values.
317 They nevertheless have high R^2 , while broadleaved forests have the lowest R^2 . The scatter
318 plots of rainfed crops and broadleaved forests show that two different clouds of sample points
319 were found (in similar location of the plots, see [Figure 6](#)), implying the presence of two
320 different vegetation species in each vegetation class. [Figure 6 near here]

321 After examining all regression results between MODIS LAI and EVI, the highest R^2
322 was estimated for the irrigated crop type, while the grassland showed moderate to high R^2 in

323 all study areas except for Rijnland, probably due to water inundation phenomena in this flat
324 landscape. Grasslands are characterized by vertical and horizontal homogeneity as well as a
325 high ground cover, and because of this, the view angle influence is considered to be minor for
326 this vegetation type (RB Myneni et al., 2002). Grassland areas are regularly mown for hay
327 production; however, this could not be verified with the available field information.

328 ***Downscaled LAI maps at the Landsat resolution***

329 The regression equations estimated using the MODIS LAI-EVI datasets were applied
330 to the Landsat EVI data for the matching dates and vegetation types. LAI maps were created
331 at the Landsat spatial resolution level for all Landsat scenes available (see [Table 3](#)). An
332 example per study area is presented in [Figure 7](#), in which minimum cloud contamination of
333 the images allowed the model to estimate LAI values for almost the entire study area in
334 Tamega and Umbeluzi, and over 2/3 of the study area in Nestos and Rijnland. [Figure 7 near
335 here]

336 A visual comparison between the MODIS LAI map of DOY 177-2013 for the study
337 area of Umbeluzi and the equivalent downscaled Landsat LAI map (DOY 177-2013) is
338 presented in [Figure 8](#). The two LAI maps are characterized by similar patterns of LAI values;
339 however, the Landsat LAI is more detailed. [Figure 9 near here]

340 ***Accuracy of the Landsat resolution LAI maps***

341 Validation of the downscaling model was performed by comparing the LAI values calculated
342 at the Landsat resolution with the available in-situ LAI data. The results of the correlation
343 analysis are presented below per study area and a full list of the associated results is provided
344 in [Table 7](#). [Table 7 near here]

345 *Nestos*

346 During April 2013, the 2 LAI images of DOY 096-2013 and 104-2013 included 4 and 5 in-
347 situ sampled locations respectively ([Table 7](#)). The correlation coefficient (r) was high for both

348 cases (0.72 for DOY 096-2013 and 0.93 for DOY 104-2013) and statistically significant at
349 0.05 level, even though the number of sampled pixels was low compared to other cases
350 examined. The RMSE was low in both cases (approximately $0.3 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$), while the mean
351 difference was also low ($0.1\text{--}0.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$), revealing a systematic over-estimation of LAI.

352 For the period of July (DOY 184-2013), r dropped to approximately 0.25, which was
353 the lowest between all datasets examined. The RMSE was also high ($1.484 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$), while the
354 mean difference was much lower ($0.054 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$) than the results of April (for both DOY 096
355 and 104).

356 *Rijnland*

357 The validation between in-situ and Landsat calculated LAI data was not possible for the
358 period of June (DOY 2013-177), since none of the field measured locations coincided with a
359 pixel of a Landsat calculated LAI value, due to heavy cloud contamination of the Landsat
360 EVI image used as input.

361 During September, the map of DOY 265-2013 included 7 samples ([Table 7](#)), for which r was
362 0.8065, statistically significant at 0.05 level. The RMSE remained moderate ($0.6511 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$),
363 while the mean difference was high ($1.776 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$) and statistically significant at 0.001 level.

364 The number of available samples increased to 15 for DOY 273-2013 resulting into a
365 moderate r (0.4801), statistically significant at 0.05 level. The RMSE increased to 1.15
366 (m^2/m^2), but the mean difference decreased to approximately half the value of DOY 265-
367 2013 ($0.87 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$), statistically significant at 0.05 level. This is due to the fact that in some
368 cases grasslands were falsely identified as agricultural areas; however, the associated in-situ
369 LAI values were similar to those estimated at the high spatial resolution level. *Tamega*

370 During May (DOY 147-2013), 21 samples were used for the correlation analysis ([Table 7](#))
371 giving moderate-low r (0.3246) and RMSE of $0.88 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$. The mean difference of LAI
372 values ($0.455 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$) was statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

373 The measurements of September (DOY 243 and 251) showed the highest correlation
374 within all areas located in Europe (Nestos, Rijnland and Tamega). Both the created LAI maps
375 of that period correlated with moderate-high r (0.636 for DOY 243-2013 and 0.643 for DOY
376 251-2013) statistically significant at 0.001 level and over 30 samples were included in both
377 cases examined. The mean difference was characterized by similarly low values (0.188 and
378 0.248 m^2/m^2 , respectively), whereas the RMSE was just above 1 m^2/m^2 in both cases.

379 *Umbeluzi*

380 During November (DOY 309-2012) the accuracy of the downscaled LAI was very low
381 ([Table 7](#)), although the sample size was larger compared to other cases examined. From the
382 10 samples examined, 3 showed a LAI value difference greater than 2 m^2/m^2 and fell into the
383 mixed vegetation category according to the field measurements (shrubs, trees and grass),
384 while Landsat classified these areas as rainfed crops in two cases and shrubs in the third.

385 Correlation analysis between the in-situ LAI values of March and those estimated at
386 the Landsat level (DOY 071-2013) was not possible, since only 2 of the in-situ LAI locations
387 coincided with the areas for which a LAI value was calculated, due to heavy cloud
388 contamination of the Landsat EVI image used as input.

389 For DOY 175-2013, r was the highest found for all cases examined (0.935,
390 statistically significant at 0.001 level), with the mean difference ($-0.2754 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$) showing
391 underestimation of the field-measured LAI. The RMSE was low (0.2013 m^2/m^2).

392 For DOY 191-2013, 16 samples were available showing an r value of 0.874,
393 statistically significant at 0.001 level, and a mean difference of $-0.192 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$, statistically
394 significant at 0.05 level. The RMSE was low (0.312 m^2/m^2), although it was slightly higher
395 as compared to DOY 175-2013.

396 **Discussion**

397 This study developed an easily applicable methodology for enhancing the coarse spatial
398 resolution LAI product of MODIS (1 km) to the Landsat resolution (30 m), using free-of-cost
399 and accessible satellite data of VIs. The accuracy of the proposed downscaling methodology
400 was evaluated across various seasons at four hydrologically and climatically diverse river
401 basins in Europe and Africa. In-situ LAI measurements of 2012-2013 available for all study
402 areas were used for the validation of the downscaling model.

403 *Overall accuracy of the downscaling model*

404 The patterns of LAI distribution in the downscaled LAI maps were evaluated as
405 reasonable, after visually examining the image pairs. Correlation analysis between the
406 downscaled and in-situ LAI for the same locations and dates, showed variability in the
407 deviations from field measurements across study areas and seasons. In general, the
408 correlation results were found to be statistically significant, even in cases with low
409 availability of samples (less than 10). In all cases where a Landsat 7 image was used in the
410 model, several sampled locations were unusable when they coincided with a data gap. In
411 most cases examined, the mean difference showed overestimation of the field measured LAI
412 compared to the calculated LAI, except for the Umbeluzi study area. The study area of
413 Umbeluzi showed consistently better results compared to the others. This mainly relates to
414 the climate of Umbeluzi, where during dry season the vegetation has uniformly low LAI and
415 EVI values. Comparison of the correlation coefficients with a similar study (Silleos et al.,
416 2014) showed improved results (for the same study areas and field-measured data), with high
417 r values (>0.7) in 5 out of 11 cases examined. Additionally, there was a slight improvement
418 in the moderate r values (0.4–0.7), as most of the cases examined in present study showed
419 moderate values over 0.5.

420 ***Study limitations***

421 Several global studies have validated the MODIS LAI product using related fieldwork, for a
422 wide range of vegetation types and time-periods, with the accuracy of the product estimated
423 at 0.66 RMSE (Root-Mean-Square-Error) LAI units in case all types of biomes were taken
424 into consideration, falling to a value of 0.5 RMSE units, when broadleaved forests were
425 excluded (R Myneni, 2012). Researchers warn that there has to be increased awareness when
426 using MODIS data, since the relation between LAI and VIs is not applicable everywhere and
427 all the time, due to measurement geometry and spatial resolution of the examined plant
428 canopies (Tian et al., 2000). Seasonality during the growth cycle of each vegetation type
429 seems to be another crucial factor when regression analysis is applied between MODIS LAI
430 and VI data. As Wang, Adiku, et al. (2005) support, during the regression analysis between
431 LAI and VI data of MODIS, R^2 values are constantly increasing during different growing
432 stages, but they also warn that assumptions and conclusions should be made only per growth-
433 cycle (over one year period), as year to other years comparison between LAI and VIs may be
434 erroneous. Meteorological conditions during different seasons is also a characteristic
435 affecting the overall quality of such data, however, by the 8-day image compositing method
436 that MODIS uses, it is possible to eliminate the contamination from cloud cover (Knyazikhin
437 et al., 1999).

438 A possible limitation of the proposed methodology could be the different days
439 (periods) of data acquisition within the composite MODIS images used for the regression
440 analysis. For instance, MODIS 8-day composite LAI values might describe vegetation
441 conditions of a different DOY compared to the values of the 16-day composite product of
442 MODIS EVI. The MODIS LAI algorithm chooses the day with the highest fPAR value to
443 assign the LAI pixel values in the associated maps. On the other hand, the highest MODIS
444 EVI value, also closer to nadir, is selected to represent the pixel values in EVI maps.

445 Consequently, in vegetation types such as irrigated or rainfed crops, where agricultural
446 activity is present, a high LAI value of a crop during the last days before harvesting might be
447 paired with a low value of EVI for the same period, if the closer to nadir EVI value coincides
448 with the days just after harvesting. The same phenomenon could also occur in dates of rapid
449 leaf green-up occurring in a period of 10-12 days (Ahl et al., 2006).

450 Low accuracies might have also occurred due to saturation of the EVI signal at high
451 biomass densities, which has been documented for other VIs too (Turner, Cohen, Kennedy,
452 Fassnacht, & Briggs, 1999). Pixels in low resolution data are likely to contain an amount of
453 radiative contribution from the background (RB Myneni et al., 2002), and while saturation
454 could explain low R^2 in the regression analysis results of needleleaved forests vegetation
455 type, this was not the case for shrubs and grassland vegetation types, since saturation is not
456 likely to affect sparse biomes (Fensholt, Sandholt, & Rasmussen, 2004). Considering
457 needleleaved forests, the results could also be affected by the presence of lower layers of
458 vegetation in areas of dense canopies, causing unsuitability of reflectance to model vegetation
459 (Fensholt et al., 2004).

460 An identified source of error was the misclassification of vegetation types across the
461 two sources of LULC data used in the downscaling model (Globcover and Landsat), which
462 was expected to a certain degree due to the different spatial resolutions used between the two
463 products. This was present in all study areas and contributed to overestimation of LAI in
464 cases where dense canopies were present (such as the broadleaved forests) and
465 underestimation of LAI in cases of low and dry vegetation (e.g., dry grassland during the
466 summer period). Relevant studies also support that the effect of misclassification is larger
467 when data of coarse spatial resolution are used (Tian et al., 2000). Moreover, for various in-
468 situ LAI locations it was proven that the vegetation type was different from the one indicated

469 by the Landsat vegetation type maps, which might have affected the correlation analysis
470 results associated with the validation of the downscaling model.

471 LAI measurements from fisheye hemispherical images might have also affected the
472 validation results of the downscaling model, since this technique has been reported to show
473 an underestimation of 25-50% as compared to direct measurements (Bréda, 2003). This is
474 mainly due to the deviation from the assumption of random distribution of the leaves, that the
475 processing software is based on. Another issue that could significantly lower the accuracy of
476 LAI measurements is the number of hemispherical photos taken in each location (Weiss,
477 Baret, Smith, Jonckheere, & Coppin, 2004). However, this has been accounted for by taking
478 from 8 to 15 hemispherical photos in each location. Finally, the issue of calibration for
479 variable illumination conditions has been accounted for with the inclusion of a procedure for
480 calibration, using the sky as reference.

481 ***Future work suggestions***

482 Variability of species within the same vegetation type, but of a different phenology,
483 could have affected the results of the regression analysis. Heterogeneity causes greater
484 underestimation levels of LAI and the magnitude of underestimation increases as vegetation
485 heterogeneity increases (Fensholt et al., 2004). Therefore, the ideal situation would be to
486 classify the data that fall into that category into more detailed vegetation classes (depending
487 on the diversity of the dominating species per study area), in order to improve the linearity of
488 the LAI-EVI relationship and succeed in estimating more accurate LAI values through the
489 downscaling model. For example, Houborg, McCabe, and Gao (2015) in their downscaling
490 methodology which uses similar datasets with the present study (MODIS LAI-NDVI and
491 Landsat products) achieved in their validation results over homogenous agricultural areas in
492 Nebraska (corn and soybean crops) high levels of agreement between their calculated high
493 resolution LAI and in-situ LAI ($R^2 > 0.80$ for all cases and timesteps examined).

494 Applying a regression model across scales (MODIS to Landsat) is involving all the
495 noises existing in high-resolution input at the final high-resolution output. This may be a
496 reason explaining some low performances. Hence, the application of a smoothing technique
497 before applying the downscaling model on high-resolution data might have been beneficial
498 for the accuracy of the relevant results. An alternative method for downscaling LAI in cases
499 of weak regression between LAI and EVI could be to use Landsat EVI regression as weights
500 to redistribute MODIS LAI values at the Landsat pixels. This has been used effectively for
501 downscaling evapotranspiration maps at similar scales (T. Alexandridis et al., 2014; Chemin
502 & Alexandridis, 2006), but could also be effective for LAI.

503 In order to improve the accuracy of the downscaling model results, Cohen,
504 Maier-sperger, Gower, and Turner (2003) propose coupling more than one VI in the
505 regression analysis. Although this could improve the overall accuracy of the downscaling
506 model, it is believed that the relevant data and the effort demanded to develop the
507 methodology would dramatically increase in volume, since the present study was applied in
508 four geographic regions and for various seasons during a whole year.

509 **Conclusions**

510 A methodology to downscale MODIS LAI data to the Landsat spatial resolution was
511 demonstrated, proving that MODIS and Landsat data are compatible for integration in the
512 same downscaling model. Limited number of pixels available for some vegetation types in
513 specific DOYs, diversity of vegetation species within the same vegetation type and
514 misclassification of vegetation types, were the most probable factors affecting the
515 downscaling model's accuracy. The created LAI maps at the Landsat spatial resolution
516 showed high visual similarity in the patterns of LAI values distribution, compared to the
517 MODIS LAI maps. Validation using in-situ LAI data showed moderate to high correlation for
518 most cases, while lower accuracies were observed during the rainy season for all the study
519 areas. The presented methodology is useful in the development of a tool for LAI estimation in

520 space and time, that is adaptable to different land cover types and geographic areas and could
521 be used for monitoring vegetation development of both natural and agricultural areas.

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525 water". MODIS and Landsat images were downloaded from USGS.

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648 **Annex I**

649 Tables with the detailed in-situ LAI measurements per period of fieldwork along with the
 650 LAI values estimated at the Landsat spatial resolution for the corresponding locations per
 651 date of interest are provided hereafter, per study area. The in-situ LAI data were acquired
 652 during 2012-2013 under FP7 EU project MyWater "Merging hydrologic models and Earth
 653 observation data for reliable information on water" (see acknowledgments). Regarding the
 654 Land Use / Land Cover (LULC) codes used in the tables, they are further explained here:
 655 LULC 21 means rainfed crops, 22 means irrigated crops, 31 means broadleaved forests, 32
 656 means needleleaved forests, 34 means shrubs and 35 means grassland.

657 Table Annex 1: Detailed list of in-situ measured LAI and corresponding LAI estimated at
 658 Landsat spatial resolution for Nestos study area per Day Of Year fieldwork took place. N/A
 659 means that due to cloud presence the downscaling model was not able to estimate a LAI
 660 value for the specified location.

Point ID	In-situ LULC	Landsat LULC	In-situ LAI DOY 99-100/2013	In-situ LAI DOY 183-184/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 096/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 104/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 184/2013
1	31	34	1.21	2.34	0.71	N/A	1.81
2	31	31	1.47	4.33	N/A	N/A	N/A
3	31	31	0.30	4.51	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	31	31	1.38	4.77	N/A	0.89	4.01
5	32	32	1.44	1.54	1.73	N/A	N/A
6	35	21	1.25	0.91	N/A	N/A	N/A
7	34	34	1.10	2.32	N/A	N/A	1.86
8	21	22	1.72	2.58	N/A	N/A	2.10
9	21	21	0.71	0.19	N/A	N/A	N/A
10	34	21	1.05	1.00	0.77	N/A	N/A
11	35	34	2.06	1.31	N/A	1.55	1.32
12	31	21	0.89	4.41	N/A	N/A	1.17
13	31	31	0.78	5.27	N/A	N/A	4.00
14	31	31	0.59	5.33	0.66	N/A	1.68
15	34	34	0.47	1.83	N/A	N/A	1.69
16	22	21	3.59	3.60	N/A	N/A	N/A
17	22	35	2.77	1.16	N/A	1.51	2.45
18	22	21	1.74	1.10	N/A	N/A	1.75
19	21	21	2.27	1.31	N/A	N/A	4.10
20	22	22	0.81	1.87	N/A	N/A	4.01
21	22	21	1.27	1.44	N/A	N/A	2.51
22	31	34	0.91	1.79	N/A	N/A	1.75
23	35	21	1.23	1.73	N/A	N/A	1.25
24	22	35	5.01	1.28	N/A	N/A	3.45

25	35	21	1.88	0.85	N/A	N/A	0.27
26	31	34	1.57	0.95	N/A	1.07	1.44
27	31	34	0.84	3.16	N/A	0.57	N/A

661

662 Table Annex 2: Detailed list of in-situ measured LAI and corresponding LAI estimated at
 663 Landsat spatial resolution for Umbeluzi study area per Day Of Year fieldwork took place.
 664 N/A means that due to cloud presence the downscaling model was not able to estimate a LAI
 665 value for the specified location.

Point ID	In-situ LULC	Landsat LULC	In-situ LAI DOY 311-313/2012	In-situ LAI DOY 182-184/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 309/2012	Landsat LAI DOY 175/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 191/2013
1	21	21	4.48	0.20	1.37	0.57	0.55
2	21	34	4.72	0.15	N/A	0.52	0.50
3	21	21	0.90	2.10	N/A	1.66	2.56
4	21	34	1.24	1.87	N/A	1.82	2.24
5	35	21	2.23	0.41	N/A	0.68	0.70
6	34	34	2.04	0.07	N/A	0.38	0.34
7	21	21	2.80	0.38	N/A	0.57	0.55
8	21	21	2.49	0.22	N/A	0.52	0.33
9	35	21	4.51	0.11	3.58	0.54	N/A
10	21	21	4.42	0.66	2.53	0.95	0.37
11	35	21	3.20	0.44	N/A	N/A	N/A
12	21	21	4.33	0.80	1.99	0.76	0.16
13	34	34	4.21	0.60	N/A	N/A	N/A
14	34	21	1.62	0.14	N/A	0.57	0.55
15	35	21	2.68	0.17	N/A	0.28	N/A
16	21	21	3.38	0.33	N/A	N/A	0.12
17	21	34	1.55	0.14	1.62	0.80	0.94
18	21	34	1.09	0.17	N/A	0.52	0.10
19	21	34	3.47	0.20	N/A	0.78	0.66
20	34	34	3.53	0.16	3.80	0.60	N/A
21	34	34	2.09	0.15	2.63	0.64	N/A
22	31	31	1.06	0.42	3.79	0.59	0.64
23	21	21	3.64	0.07	2.24	0.42	N/A
24	31	31	3.36	0.60	2.88	0.77	N/A

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670 Table Annex 3: Detailed list of in-situ measured LAI and corresponding LAI estimated at
 671 Landsat spatial resolution for Tamega study area per Day Of Year fieldwork took place. N/A
 672 means that due to cloud presence the downscaling model was not able to estimate a LAI
 673 value for the specified location.

Point ID	In-situ LULC	Landsat LULC	In-situ LAI DOY 140-143/2013	In-situ LAI DOY 245-248/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 147/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 243/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 251/2013
1	34	34	0.91	2.66	N/A	N/A	3.38
2	31	32	1.98	2.20	2.37	2.31	1.97
3	32	32	1.59	1.62	1.71	1.90	1.78
4	32	32	3.87	3.21	2.96	2.83	2.40
5	32	32	2.53	4.81	2.45	1.96	1.89
6	34	34	2.63	4.69	2.04	2.19	2.25
7	32	32	2.58	2.49	N/A	3.04	2.79
8	32	32	0.92	1.68	N/A	1.02	1.09
9	31	32	1.43	1.96	N/A	2.26	2.09
10	34	34	0.97	1.52	2.91	2.82	2.69
11	32	32	4.15	4.98	N/A	2.76	2.83
12	34	32	1.08	1.65	2.50	2.40	2.06
13	34	34	0.86	0.69	2.04	0.93	0.94
14	34	34	1.01	2.56	2.52	2.20	2.22
15	34	34	1.72	3.80	2.00	1.96	2.12
16	34	34	1.18	2.17	0.97	0.84	0.86
17	34	34	0.47	0.19	N/A	N/A	N/A
18	34	34	3.37	1.18	2.11	1.34	1.17
19	31	31	1.46	1.38	2.37	1.50	1.63
20	34	34	0.91	0.79	N/A	0.89	1.02
21	22	22	0.24	0.99	0.82	1.49	1.65
22	22	22	0.37	1.29	1.30	1.31	1.41
23	35	21	1.72	0.29	N/A	0.47	0.46
24	21	21	1.71	0.09	4.11	0.03	0.13
25	22	22	0.85	2.15	N/A	3.67	3.87
26	22	22	1.82	0.73	0.89	1.15	1.06
27	35	21	3.89	0.66	N/A	0.81	0.79
28	31	31	1.07	3.49	2.96	4.68	4.83
29	22	22	1.17	0.67	1.20	1.12	0.99
30	22	21	0.01	3.32	N/A	1.65	1.73
31	35	21	1.44	2.03	N/A	1.59	1.51
32	22	22	1.39	0.40	1.18	1.05	0.75
33	34	34	0.61	0.18	N/A	0.46	0.21
34	22	22	2.30	5.00	N/A	N/A	3.66
35	31	31	1.52	3.41	N/A	2.42	1.98
36	32	34	2.28	0.32	2.47	N/A	0.16
37	21	21	2.12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

675 Table Annex 4: Detailed list of in-situ measured LAI and corresponding LAI estimated at
 676 Landsat spatial resolution for Rijnland study area per Day Of Year fieldwork took place. N/A
 677 means that due to cloud presence the downscaling model was not able to estimate a LAI
 678 value for the specified location.

Point ID	In-situ LULC	Landsat LULC	In-situ LAI DOY 266-269/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 265/2013	Landsat LAI DOY 273/2013
1	35	35	0.56	N/A	1.11
2	32	32	5.71	N/A	N/A
3	32	32	3.74	N/A	N/A
4	32	32	4.67	N/A	2.32
5	32	32	3.91	N/A	N/A
6	31	34	3.91	N/A	0.96
7	32	21	5.62	4.79	4.17
8	32	31	5.94	N/A	4.00
9	35	35	1.61	N/A	0.32
10	21	21	3.35	1.26	4.20
11	35	21	2.28	N/A	N/A
12	21	21	4.71	1.52	3.98
13	21	21	3.74	N/A	3.74
14	21	21	4.31	N/A	2.27
15	21	21	3.10	1.57	2.02
16	35	21	1.27	N/A	0.95
17	21	21	3.48	1.55	4.03
18	21	21	0.13	N/A	N/A
19	35	21	2.81	N/A	1.58
20	21	21	3.17	1.72	3.58
21	21	21	0.61	N/A	N/A
22	21	21	1.35	N/A	N/A
23	21	21	0.09	N/A	N/A
24	31	31	5.97	N/A	N/A
25	21	21	3.08	1.66	N/A

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681 **Tables:**

682 Table 1. Description of key characteristics per study area.

Study area	Climate	Natural vegetation	Agricultural vegetation
Nestos, Greece (Europe)	Mediterranean	Coniferous and broadleaved forests, shrubs and grassland.	Mainly single-cycle crops (both irrigated and rainfed).
Umbeluzi, Mozambique (Africa)	Warm Tropical	Mixture of sparse small sized (<1.5 m) trees and bushes (shrubs), a few broadleaved trees, grassland.	Mainly rainfed fields, a few but large-sized irrigated fields with tree crops.
Tamega, Portugal (Europe)	Warm Temperate – Mediterranean	Mixture of coniferous and broadleaved forests, shrubs, grassland.	Mainly rainfed single-cycle crops, a few irrigated fields in the southern part of the basin
Rijnland, the Netherlands (Europe)	Temperate Oceanic	Mainly broadleaved and a few coniferous trees, herbaceous vegetation in the sand dunes, large settlements with green space.	Mainly pasture for grazing and other single-cycle crops. Greenhouses also present.

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685 Table 2. MODIS LAI and EVI images per Day Of Year (DOY) acquired, according to in-situ
 686 LAI data availability.

Study Area	Product	DOY	Total images per DOY
Nestos	LAI, EVI	097-2013	2
	LAI, EVI	177-2013	2
Rijnland	LAI, EVI	177-2013	2
	LAI, EVI	273-2013	2
Tamega	LAI, EVI	145-2013	2
	LAI, EVI	241-2013	2
Umbeluzi	LAI, EVI	305-2012	2
	LAI, EVI	065-2013	2
	LAI, EVI	177-2013	2
	LAI, EVI	193-2013	2

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690 Table 3. Landsat EVI images acquired, according to in-situ LAI data availability.

Study Area	Satellite	DOY	Landsat Tile Cloud Coverage
Nestos	Landsat 7	096-2013	55–60%
	Landsat 8	104-2013	75–80%
	Landsat 8	184-2013	40–45%
Rijnland	Landsat 8	177-2013	75-80%
	Landsat 7	265-2013	70–75%
	Landsat 8	273-2013	10–15%
Tamega	Landsat 7	147-2013	70–75%
	Landsat 7	243-2013	5–10%
	Landsat 8	251-2013	5–10%
Umbeluzi	Landsat 8	309-2012	40-50%
	Landsat 8	071-2013	75-80%
	Landsat 8	175-2013	<5%
	Landsat 8	191-2013	55–60%

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692 Table 4. Available in-situ LAI measurements per Day Of Year (DOY) and study area.

Study Area	DOY	Measured Locations
Nestos	99-100/2013	27
	183-184/2013	27
Rijnland	177-179/2013	25
	266-269/2013	25
Tamega	140-143/2013	37
	245-248/2013	36
Umbeluzi	311-313/2012	24
	71-73/2013	22
	182-184/2013	24

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694 Table 5. Wavelengths (in micrometres) of Blue, Red and NIR bands for MODIS and Landsat
 695 sensors.

Sensor	Blue Band	Red Band	NIR band
MODIS	0.459–0.479	0.62–0.67	0.841–0.876
Landsat ETM+	0.45–0.52	0.63–0.69	0.77–0.90
Landsat OLI	0.45–0.51	0.64–0.67	0.85–0.88

696

697 Table 6. Regression analysis results ($p < 0.0001$) including offset and slope of the linear
 698 equation for Umbeluzi (DOY 193-2013) per vegetation type. R^2 is the coefficient of
 699 determination and N the number of samples.

Vegetation Type	R^2	N	offset	slope
Rainfed crops	0.52	785	-0.5493	5.2105
Broadleaved forests	0.39	666	-0.3158	4.1828
Shrubs	0.58	242	-0.3357	4.1365
Grassland	0.79	305	-0.3568	4.3890

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701 Table 7. Correlation analysis results of the estimated LAI values at Landsat spatial resolution
 702 against in-situ data. *r* is the coefficient of correlation and RMSE is the Root Mean Square
 703 Error.

Study area	Landsat LAI DOY	Number of field locations	<i>r</i>	RMSE (m ² /m ²)	Mean difference (m ² /m ²)
Nestos	096-2013	4	0.7209*	0.3049	0.1051*
	104-2013	5	0.9275*	0.3151	0.6048*
	184-2013	19	0.2542	1.484	0.0544
Rijnland	265-2013	7	0.8065*	0.6511	1.7764**
	273-2013	15	0.4801*	1.1576	0.8693*
Tamega	147-2013	21	0.3246	0.8809	0.4551*
	243-2013	32	0.6366**	1.0825	0.1888
	251-2013	35	0.6428**	1.0593	0.2486
Umbeluzi	309-2012	10	-0.1783	1.3419	0.6534
	175-2013	21	0.935**	0.2013	-0.2754**
	191-2013	16	0.874**	0.3127	-0.1924*

p* = statistically significant at 0.05 level *p* = statistically significant at ≤ 0.001 level

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705 **Figures:**

Figure 1.

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Legend:

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|---|---------------------|---|-----------------------|
| | In-situ LAI locations |
| | Needle-leaved forests |
| | Shrubs |
| | | | Grassland |

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Figure 2.

Figure 3.

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Figure 5.

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Figure 6.

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Figure 7.

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Figure 8.

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744 **List of Figures:**

745 Figure 1. Geographic distribution of study sites.

746 Figure 2. Land-cover maps at Landsat spatial resolution (30 m) for: (a) Nestos, (b) Umbeluzi,
747 (c) Tamega and (d) Rijnland study areas.

748 Figure 3. Preview of the data used in the rescaling process of a Landsat tile (Day Of Year
749 251-2013) rescaled to the MODIS 1 km pixel resolution, for the Tamega study area. (a)
750 shows a Landsat cloud-free tile, (b) shows the MODIS (1km x 1km) fishnet and (c) shows a
751 detailed overlay view of the MODIS fishnet on a Landsat tile.

752 Figure 4. Flowchart of the methodology followed for the downscaling model.

753 Figure 5. Statistical analysis and comparison of EVI values between MODIS (y-axis) and
754 Landsat (x-axis) data for the study areas of (a) Tamega (MODIS DOY 2013-257) and (b)
755 Umbeluzi (MODIS DOY 2013-177). N is the number of sample points and R^2 is the
756 coefficient of determination.

757 Figure 6. Scatter plots and linear models for MODIS LAI (y-axis) against MODIS EVI (x-
758 axis) on Day Of Year 2013-193 for the Umbeluzi study area and per vegetation type present.
759 R^2 is the coefficient of determination and N is the number of sample points.

760 Figure 7. LAI maps at Landsat resolution (30 m) for: (a) Nestos (DOY 184/2013), (b)
761 Umbeluzi (DOY 175/2013), (c) Tamega (DOY 251/2013) and (d) Rijnland (DOY 273/2013)
762 study areas. The white gaps appearing in the maps indicate areas with no data due to cloud
763 presence.

764 Figure 8. Comparison of spatial resolution characteristics in Umbeluzi between: (a) a MODIS
765 LAI image (DOY 177-2013) and (b) a downscaled at Landsat resolution LAI image (DOY
766 175-2013).

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